

**Synthesis of some New Mannich Bases,
Sulphides and Disulphides of 1,3,4-Oxadiazol-
2-thiones as Potential Antifungal Agents**

R. K. TEWARI**, R. K. MISHRA**,
SHISHIR K. SRIVASTAVA and S. C. BAHTEL*

Department of Chemistry, University of Gorakhpur,
Gorakhpur-273 009

*Manuscript received 27 March 1990, revised 14 November 1990,
accepted 6 December 1990*

VARIOUS 3,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones and several benzidine derivatives display biological activities^{1,2}. Several oxadiazolyl sulphides and disulphides also exhibit biological activity³. In view of these observations the title compounds, viz. the sulphides, disulphides, benzidine and piperazine derivatives and Mannich bases of substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones have been prepared to evaluate their biological activities against two fungi, viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

Thus, 3-arylaminoethyl or ethyl-5-aryl/aryloxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (1-11) were prepared by condensation of 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones in methanol with aldehydes and arylamines. The corresponding bis-Mannich bases (12-22) were prepared by condensation of the oxadiazol-2-thiones with aldehyde and benzidine/piperazine.

** Department of Chemistry, St. Andrew's (P G) College, Gorakhpur-273 001.

NOTES

Alkyl oxadiazolyl sulphides (23-26) were prepared from the 2-thiones by treatment with alkyl bromides and fused sodium acetate, whereas the disulphides (27-30) were synthesised by oxidation of the 2-thiones with bromine (Scheme 1). Structures of the compounds were characterised by elemental analyses and ¹H nmr data of only one representative compound of the aminoalkyl and benzidine derivatives.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 710 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at 90 MHz. The reactions were monitored by tlc. The required 5-aryl/aryloxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones were prepared by known method⁴. The preparative details and data of only one compound of each class are described in the sequel. The results are given in Table 1.

3-Arylaminoalkyl derivative (1): To an ice-cold solution of 5-aryl/aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (0.01 mol) in methanol, was added formaldehyde/acetaldehyde (0.01 mol) followed by a cold methanolic solution of arylamine (0.01 mol) with

Scheme 1 Reagents: (i) R¹CHO, R²NH₂, MeOH, (ii) R¹CHO, benzidine/piperazine, MeOH, (iii) R¹Br/ACONa, MeOH, (iv) Br₂, MeOH

stirring. The mixture was then left in the ice-bath for 3 h and the resulting solid was washed with cold methanol and crystallised from aqueous ethanol to

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no	R	R ¹	R ²	Yield %	M p °C	Molecular formula
1	2-Cl, 5-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	H	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	51	166	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
2	2-Cl, 5-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	H	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	60	177	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
3	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	H	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	80	192	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
4	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	CH ₃	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	70	260	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
5	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	H	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	81	169	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
6	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	77	88	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
7	4-OHC ₆ H ₄ -	H	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	67	130	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
8	4-OHC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	51	48	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
9	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ OCH ₂ -	H	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	52	142	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ S
10	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ OCH ₂ -	CH ₃	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	66	95	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ S
11	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ OCH ₂ -	H	3,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	62	128	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
	R	R ¹	X			
12	2-Cl, 5-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	H	4-HN-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH-4	78	235	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂
13	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -	H	-N(CH ₂) ₄ N-	61	>300	C ₃₂ H ₁₈ N ₁₀ O ₁₀ S ₂
14	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	H	4-HN-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH-4	81	177	C ₃₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
15	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	4-HN-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH-4	76	140	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
16	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	H	-N(CH ₂) ₄ N-	83	223	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
17	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂) ₄ N-	81	149	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
18	4-OHC ₆ H ₄ -	H	4-HN-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH-4	69	155	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
19	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ OCH ₂ -	H	4-HN-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH-4	74	150	C ₄₀ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
20	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ OCH ₂ -	CH ₃	4-HN-(C ₆ H ₄) ₂ -NH-4	66	147	C ₄₂ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
21	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ OCH ₂ -	H	-N(CH ₂) ₄ N-	62	138	C ₃₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
22	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ OCH ₂ -	CH ₃	-N(CH ₂) ₄ N-	60	133	C ₃₄ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
	R	R ¹				
23	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂ -		74	47	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
24	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ -		66	53	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
25	4-OHC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂ -		63	160	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
26	4-OHC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ -		53	125	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
	R					
27	2-Cl, 5-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -			54	213	C ₁₆ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂
28	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ -			74	>300	C ₁₆ H ₆ N ₄ O ₁₀ S ₂
29	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -			83	196	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
30	4-OHC ₆ H ₄ -			52	185	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂

*C, H, N and S analyses of all compounds were found satisfactory

yield **1** (51%), m.p. 166° (Found : N, 14.22 ; S, 8.09. $C_{17}H_{15}ClN_4O_3S$ requires : N, 14.34 ; S, 8.20%) ; ν_{max} 3 350 (NH), 1 520 (C=N), 1 370 (C-CH₃), 1 320 (C-NO₂), 1 080 (C=S) and 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ 2.25 and 2.35 (6H, s each, 2 × ArCH₃), 5.65 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, CH₂), 7.0–7.9 (6H, m, ArH) and 8.5 (1H, s, NH).

Benzidine derivative (14) : It was prepared similarly as in case of **1–11** except that 5 equivalents of the amine were used, and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (81%), m.p. 177° (Found : N, 13.32 ; S, 10.13. $C_{32}H_{28}N_6O_4S_2$ requires : N, 13.46 ; S, 10.26%) ; ν_{max} 3 350 (NH), 1 520 (C=N), 1 040, 1 260 (=C-O-C) and 1 100 cm⁻¹ (C=S) ; δ 3.7 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃), 5.6 (4H, d, J 7 Hz, 2 × CH₂) and 7.1–8.0 (18H, m, ArH and NH).

Oxadiazolyl sulphide (23) : A mixture of methanolic solution of the 2-thione (0.01 mol), alkyl bromide (0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (2.00 g) was refluxed gently for 4 h and then poured into cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (74%), m.p. 47° (Found : N, 11.08 ; S, 12.92. $C_{12}H_{14}N_2O_2S$ requires : N, 11.20 ; S, 12.80%) ; ν_{max} 1 500 (C=N), 1 380 (C-CH₃), 1 020, 1 260 (=C-O-C) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C).

Disulphide (27) : To an ice-cold methanolic solution of the 2-thione (0.01 mol) a cold methanolic solution of bromine (0.005 mol) was added dropwise with swirling. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (54%), m.p. 213° (Found : N, 16.21 ; S, 12.58. $C_{16}H_6Cl_2N_6O_6S_2$ requires : N, 16.37 ; S, 12.48%) ; ν_{max} 1 500 (C=O), 1 340 (C-NO₂) and 760 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl).

Antifungal screening : All the compounds were screened by agar growth technique² against two fungi, viz. *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at concentrations 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. A commercial fungicide carbendazim was also tested for comparison.

On the basis of average percentage inhibitions observed after 96 h it may be concluded that at all three doses, the compounds were less active than the standard carbendazim. Only at the dose of 1000 ppm compounds **1–11**, **15**, **20**, **22** and **27** showed 80% activity (compared to the standard) against both the fungi. On an average the compounds showed 45–50% and <40% activity at doses of 100 and 10 ppm respectively against both the fungi. In general, the presence of chlorine, nitro, alkoxy and/or aryloxy groups invariably increased the fungitoxicity of the compounds.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Gorakhpur, and the Principal, St. Andrew's (P.G.) College, Gorakhpur for facilities, Dr. P. K. Singh, Department of Chemistry, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, U.S.A.

for elemental analyses and ir spectra and Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for nmr spectra. One of the authors (S.K.S.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. A. K. SENGUPTA, M. GARG and U. CHANDRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1230 ; A. E. LIPKIN, I. S. CHICHKANOVA and T. A. DEGTYAREVA, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1970, **4**, 18 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **74**, 12725) ; B. N. GOSWAMI, J. C. S. KATAKY, J. N. BARUAH and S. C. NATH, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1984, **21**, 205.
2. V. K. MISHRA and S. C. BABEL, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1984, **117**, 357.
3. S. GIRI, H. SINGH and L. D. S. YADAV, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1976, **40**, 17 ; S. P. SUMAN and S. C. BABEL, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1979, **43**, 1339.
4. R. M. YOUNG and K. H. WOOD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 400.